

SAGA's Relevance and Impact

Cultural Heritage is acknowledged as a significant contributor to sustainable economic development¹ as well as being a positive force for building social cohesion². Furthermore, UNESCO recognises that cultural heritage acts as both a driver and enabler for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (in particular, SDGs 4, 5, 8, 10, 11, 13, 16, 17)³.

Thus, nations have an obligation to sustainably manage, preserve and present their cultural heritage that is enshrined in the Convention on the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage (1972)⁴ and the European Convention for the Protection of the Archaeological Heritage (revised) (Valletta, 1992)⁵. Land use pressures and environmental change present immediate and significant threats to future cultural heritage management and preservation⁶. The challenge for cultural heritage management is that a significant proportion of tangible cultural heritage is buried below-ground with little or no visible expression at the ground surface. Identification of this buried resource is difficult and protecting an unknown resource presents special challenges.

Geophysics provides non-destructive methods for identifying, understanding and even monitoring the condition of, buried archaeological remains. However, challenges remain in the optimisation and interpretation of geophysical signals and to date the techniques have not been widely adopted for archaeological survey or management. SAGA brings together a network of geophysicists, archaeologists, soil scientists and a wide range of experts in other geoscience sub-disciplines to make a major push forward in our capability to interpret geophysical data for archaeological purposes. In so doing, SAGA will make a significant contribution to our ability to identify, interpret and monitor archaeological remains as part of a holistic strategy for cultural heritage management and preservation.

References

1. UNESCO (2014) Culture, Creativity and Sustainable Development. Research, Innovation, Opportunities. 3rd UNESCO World Forum (Florence) on Culture and Cultural Industries, CLT/CRE/DCE/2014/1.
2. UNESCO (2013) The Hangzhou Declaration 'Placing Culture at the Heart of Sustainable Development Policies'. International Congress "Culture: Key to Sustainable Development", Hangzhou, May 2013.
3. UNESCO (2013) Ministerial declaration of the 2013 high-level segment of the Economic and Social Council, entitled "Science, technology and innovation, and the potential of culture, for promoting sustainable development and achieving the Millennium Development Goals" E/2013/L.18.
4. UNESCO (1972) Convention on the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage (Paris, 1972).
5. Council of Europe (1992) Convention for the Protection of the Archaeological Heritage of Europe (revised) (Valletta, 1992), ETS No. 143.
6. Markham, A., Osipova, E., Lafrenz Samuels, L. & Caldas, A. (2016) World Heritage and Tourism in a Changing Climate. UNEP, Nairobi, Kenya, and UNESCO, Paris, France.